

A CASE STUDY ON AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF SHWITRA***¹Dr. Aparna Waghmare, ²Dr. Dattatratya G. Parde, ³Dr. Tirunagari Yadagiri Swamy**¹PG Scholar, Department of Kaumarbhritya, Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Dharashiv, Maharashtra, India.²Assistant Profesor, Department of Kaumarbhritya, Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Dharashiv, Maharashtra, India.³HOD and Professor, Department of Kaumarbhritya, Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Dharashiv, Maharashtra, India.

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ABSTRACT

Shwitra is a condition characterised by white patches on the body. It's possible that it's linked to Vitiligo in modern science. In Ayurveda, all skin illnesses are classified as Kustha Roga. It is caused by Tridosha vitiation. It is an autoimmune disease that can be linked to other autoimmune diseases such as diabetes mellitus, pernicious anaemia, and Addison disease. Leukoderma affects one percent of the population. For the patient, this sickness becomes a source of social disgrace as well as a financial hardship. **Aim:** To Evaluate the Efficacy of Ayurvedic Treatment In Shwitra. **Study Design:** Simple Single Arm Study. **Place:** Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Dharashiv, Maharashtra. **Duration of study:** 3 Months. **Methodology:** Kosthashuddhi With Internal Medication (Aamapachaka vati and Vidangarishta) after Kosthashuddhi Rasamanikya And Rasaaushidhi, For External Medication (Bakuchi churna + Tamrabhasma + Hartal Bhasma + Mansheela mixed with Gomutra.) Which provides a hope in efficient and safe treatment. It was in much better shape than before.

KEYWORDS: Shwitra, kustha roga, Rasamanikya, Mansheela, rasausadhi.

1. INTRODUCTION

Our body's largest organ, the skin, forms the outermost covering of our body. It is a complicated organ that interacts physiologically and pathologically with the majority of other organs. UV protection is provided by the pigment melanin. Our body's largest organ is our skin. The condition of one's skin, encompassing physical and psychological health, determines one's beauty and attraction. Shwitra is a skin illness that has a significant negative impact on human existence. The Shwitra is a group of symptoms that appear as white spots on the skin and generate a cosmetic imbalance in the body. Which leads to make many of social psychological stigmas in the patient's life.

White, red, or copper red coloured spots on the skin, loss of skin lustre, loss and colouring of hair, roughness, dryness, itching, and burning feeling of the patches are all signs and symptoms of Shwitra. It was linked to vitiligo and leukoderma, according to modern research.

Leukoderma is defined as skin depigmentation caused by the destruction of melanocytes in the body, which can be localised or full. Leukoderma looks a lot like vitiligo, which is characterised by white patches on the skin. Thyroid disease, diabetes mellitus, Addison's disease, traumatic occurrences, eczema, and psoriasis are all examples of autoimmune conditions that can cause leukoderma. Leukoderma is not a painful, harmful, or contagious condition, but it has a significant psychological impact on the individual who suffers from it. The size of leukoderma patches varies.^[1]

It is a psycho-emotional disease reflected in the skin as pigmentation problem. In today's world everyone is beauty conscious. White patches that appear on the skin exhibit beauty mainly in females. It degrades the moral of a person with regards to beauty and also leads to lack in confidence.

The following case was treated for three months with administration of Internal medication and rasaushadhi, with excellent results as evidenced by inspection and photographs. The results of this clinical trial will shed more light on the effects of Ayurvedic medicine on leukoderma.

1.1. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To evaluate the efficacy of Ayurvedic treatment in Shwitra.

2. CASE DESCRIPTION

In May 2025, a female patient aged 6 years, opd reg. no.2500018888 visited opd of kaumarbhritya, Government ayurvedic hospital, with white discoloration over lower abdomen in periumbilical region and hypochondriac region and lower back since 2 years, minor itching, dryness presented to opd of kaumarbhritya, Government hospital. Dharashiv.

3. HISTORY OF PRESENT ILLNESS

Before 2 years, the patient was in good health. She gradually acquired some white discoloration on lower back side. The patient was unconcerned about it and ignored it, but her mother saw more white patches on lower abdomen periumbilical region and hypochondriac region. Which presented with severe itching, dryness, and the color of the patches were white. After that patient's parents took her nearby hospital. There she was diagnosed with vitiligo and given suitable medicine her. The patient took couple of months treatment but she did not get relief. To get a suitable solution they visited our hospital Government Ayurved hospital for further management.

PAST HISTORY

No history of above skin complaints from past 2 year.

No any history of thyroid disorder or any metabolic disorder.

FAMILY HISTORY

No history of same family illness.

IMMUNIZATION STATUS

Immunization taken as per schedule for this age.

PERSONAL HISTORY

Urine: 4-5 Times/Day

Sleep: Sound

Krida: Outdoor

SOCIAL HISTORY

Residential Area: Rural

Personal Hygiene: Poor

Sanitation: Poor

Drinking Water: Tubewell

DEVELOPMENTAL STATUS**Gross Motor:** Achieved**Fine Motor:** Achieved**Personal and Social:** Achieved**Language:** Achieved**Toilet Training:** Achieved**DIETETIC HISTORY**

Vegetarian diet + Non vegetarian

CLINICAL ASSESSMENT**a. General examination****Heart Rate:** 88/M**Temperature:** 98.8 F**Respiratory Rate:** 20/M**b. Systemic Examination****Respiratory System:** AEBE Normal**Cardiovascular System:** S₁S₂ Normal**GIT System:** P/A Soft and Non-Tender**Central Nervous System:** Patient Was

Conscious and Oriented

LOCAL EXAMINATION**Site of lesion:** lower abdomen near umbilical region and hypochondriac region and lower back sides.**Distribution:** focal asymmetrical and diffused in some parts.**Colour:** White**Itching:** Present**Severity:** severe**Discharge:** Absent**Superficial sensation on lesion:** Normal sensation**Pain:** Absent**Swelling:** Absent

DASHVIDH PARIKSHAN**Prakriti:** Pitta Kaphaj**Satmya:** Madhyama,**Vikriti:** Rasa, Rakta, Mansa, Meda**Aharashakti:** Madhyama**Sara:** Madhyama**Vyayama Shakti:** Madhyama**Samhanana:** Madhyama**Vaya:** Baalavastha**Satva:** Madhyama**Pramana:** Madhyama**4. MATERIAL AND METHOD****4.1 Centre of Study**

This study was carried out in kaumarbhritya department of Government Ayurvedic Hospital, Dharashiv.

4.2 Treatment

Medication has given to the patient for 3 months with 3 follow from 0 day to 90 day.

Table No 1: Treatment Plan.

1 st cycle	2 nd cycle	3 rd cycle
Amapachak vati ½ bd for 5 days before meal Vidnagarishta 5 ml bd for 15 day		
Twak rasyana 35 gms+ Arogyavardhini vati 14+ Gandhak rasyan 7 tab+ rasmaniyka 3 gms=1gm churna bd for 21 days with madhe	Twak rasyana 35 gms+ Arogyavardhini vati 14+ Gandhak rasyana7 tab+ rasmaniyka3 gms = churna bd for 21 days with madhu	Twak rasyana 35 gma+ A rogyavardhini vati 14+ Gandhak rasyana7 tab+ rasmaniyka 3 gms= 1 gm churna bd for 21 days with madhu
Bahyachikitisa Bakuchi churna 100gms+tamra bhasma5 gms+hartal bhasma5gms+ mansheel bhasma 10 gms =with gomtura lepa &aatap sewan For 21 days	Bahyachikitisa Bakuchi churna 100gms+tamra bhasma5 gms+hartal bhasma5gms+ mansheel bhasma 10 gms =with gomtura lepa &aatap sewan For 21 days	Bahyachikitisa Bakuchi churna 100gms+tamra bhasma5 gms+hartal bhasma5gms+ mansheel bhasma 10 gms =with gomtura lepa & aatap sewan For 21 days
Yashtimadhu Ghrita for lepanarth	Yashtimadhu Ghrita for lepanarth	Yashtimadhu Ghrita for lepanarth

5. OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Regular oral and external use of medication was observed Which help in minimize the size of the shwitra patches and colour of the patches.

Table No 2: Assessment Grading for subjective parameter.

Sr no	Colour of patch	Size of patches	Number of black spots appeared in patch	Score
1	Normal skin color	Absent patch	Non appearance of black spot	0
2	Rakta	<10cm	5 to 10 spots	1
3	Tamra	10_15cm patch	10to 20 spots	2
4	Shwet	>15cm patch	>20 spots	3

Table No 3: Observation during treatment for number of black spots in observed patch.

Sr.no	Number of black spots appeared in observed patch	1 st cycle	2 nd cycle	3 rd cycle
1	None			
2	5 to 10 spots	1		
3	10to 20 spots		2	
4	20spots		3	3

Table No 4: Observation during treatment for color of patches.

Sr.no.	Colour of patch	1 st cycle	2 nd cycle	3 rd cycle
1	Normal skin color		Light normal skin color appearing	Normal skin color appeared and light white patch present in some part
2	Rakta	2		
3	Tamra			
4	Shwet	3		

Table No 5: Observation during treatment.

Sr.no	Size of patches	1 st cycle	2 nd cycle	3 rd cycle
1	Absent patch			0
2	<10 cm		1	1
3	10 to 15 cms	2	2	
4	>15 cm	3		

RESULT

1. After the treatment the color patches gradually becomes appearing normal skin color
2. Size of patch gradually decreased in size and itching is completely stop
3. No new patches are observed.

Symptopms	Percentage
Twak shwetata	70%
Twak kandu	100%

PATCH BEFORE TREATMENT

PATCHES AFTER TREATMENT

6. DISCUSSION

The ayurvedic regimen we used in this case started with amapachak vati for Deepan Pachan that after Vidangarishta as krimighna purpose.

6.1 Twak Rasyana

Its constituents Nimb, Guduchi, hartiki, amalaki, vidanga, musta, sariva, daruharidra, in sam bhaga and shunthi ardhbhag these drugs have properties of twachya in classics. In which amalaki has vitamin c which enhances the late differentiation of keratinocytes, reduced oxidative stress and keeps the integrity of the entire cuticle. Which ensures the characteristics of the skin barrier and stops pores and skin water loss, which helps in help in flip the problem.

6.2 Vidangarishta

we used it act as anti protozoal also has energetic concept i.e estrogenic factor which accelerates the tyrosinase activity of human melanocyte, and promotes the formation of melanin.

6.3 Gandhak Rasyana^[2]

1. Composition

Shuddha Gandhak (purified Sulphur) with repeated Bhavana (triturations) using herbal decoctions like Guduchi, Triphala, Chaturjat, etc.

2. Properties (Guna-Karma)

Rasayana: Rejuvenates skin tissues.

Kushtaghna: Effective in all types of skin diseases.

Raktashodhaka: Purifies blood and removes toxins.

Krimighna: Destroys microbial/parasite infestations.

6.4 Arogyavardhini Vati^[3]

Liver detoxification (Yakrit Shuddhi): Improves metabolism, clears toxins responsible for skin eruptions.

Rakta Shodhana (Blood Purification): Removes accumulated dosas from blood, reduces inflammation and discoloration.

Dosha Shamana: Pacifies Pitta & Kapha dosha → reduces itching, scaling, and discharge.

Rasayana effect: Nourishes tissues, strengthens immunity, prevents recurrence.

6.4 Rasmaninkya^[4]

It contains hartal which has following properties.

Dosha-Dushyaa Shodhana: Rasamanikya helps clear Ama and purifies Rakta dhatu.

Corrects Agni & metabolism: Prevents improper Dhatu poshana, restoring pigment production.

Pigmentation support: By balancing Pitta and Rakta, it indirectly stimulates melanogenesis. Works best when combined with Bakuchi, Khadira, Gandhak Rasayan, and Arogyavardhini Vati.

6.5 Lepa

we used bakuchi + hartal bhasma + Tamra bhasma + manshila bhasm.

Bakuchi: Stimulates melanogenesis

Hartala: Breaks the pathogenesis of shwitra destruction of which prevent melanocytes. The self the vyavayi and ashukari properties of hartala may help the other drugs to reach the site quickly_ and remove the obstruction of shwitra.^[5]

Mansheela: Act as a toxic warmth on skin which promote the quick absorption of other drugs. It also has katurasa, ushnavirya, saraguna which helps in vata-kapha shaman and also varnya karma act on bharajak pitta which mainly involved in colouration of skin.^[6]

Tamra Bhasma: Kushtaghna properties local detoxification.

6.7 Yashtimadhu Ghrita

Pitta-Rakta Shamana: Reduces inflammation and corrects dushti in Rakta dhatu.

Varnya & Tvachya: Enhances complexion and supports pigment formation.

Rasayana Effect: Nourishes dhatus, strengthens immunity, prevents recurrence.

Ghrita as Vehicle: Improves absorption, penetrates up to cellular level, ensures sustained effect.

Soothing Effect: Reduces itching, dryness, burning, and psychological distress.

7. CONCLUSION

Shwitra (lucoderma) is one of the skin ailments producing psychosomatic trauma to individual and it is of more concern especially in children ayurveda remedies have highest potential to control shwitra. In this study encouraging results was obtained in shwitra. There is significant reduction in the patches with use ayurved regimen we used is found to be safe and effective.

8. REFERENCES

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